

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OIL AND GAS REVENUES AND BUDGET BASED HEALTH EXPENDITURES DURING 2000 – 2019

Babashli E.,

doctoral student,

Republic of Turkey Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University,

Institute of Social Sciences

ORCID: 0000-0002-6055-8423 Baku, Azerbaijan

Babashov A.,

PhD in Economics, Associate professor,

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction,

Department of "Industrial Organization and Management",

Aliyev R.

PhD in Economics, Associate professor,

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction,

Department of "Industrial Organization and Management",

Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Institute of Economics Department of "Fiscal and Monetary

Regulation Problems"

ORCID: 0000-0002-0651-4913 Baku, Azerbaijan

ABSTRACT

After gaining independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan, rich in natural resources, started to generate significant oil and gas revenues since the beginning of the 2000s. Striving for economic growth, sustainable development and social welfare, the country has established the State Oil Fund (SOFAZ) to manage resource revenues. The earnings accumulated within SOFAZ during the last twenty years have played a determining role in the financing of the country's crucial infrastructure projects and the state budget. Since 2014, the sharp fluctuations in oil prices have negatively affected all areas of the Azerbaijani economy, including the health sector, and demonstrated that the country is highly dependent on natural resources. Despite the crisis, the country insisted on achieving its objectives and has been increasing the number of financial resources allocated for expenditures of one of the decisive components of human capital, the health sector, each year. This paper aims to investigate the causality relationship between oil and natural gas revenues and state budget health expenditures for period between the years 2000 and 2019. As a result of the research, the existence of a linear and positive relationship between the two indicators, which has an important explanatory level, has been revealed.

Keywords: Republic of Azerbaijan, Oil and gas revenues, Budget health expenditures, Resource dependency, State Oil Fund of Azerbaijan Republic (SOFAZ).

Introduction

In our globalizing world, human capital—one of the fundamental components of economic growth and development—is gaining increasing importance. One of the foundational elements supporting the development of human capital is the enhancement of health expenditures in both quantitative and qualitative terms. This process operates as a closed-loop cyclical structure, whereby increased health spending facilitates economic growth and development.

While various factors determine a country's level of health expenditure, the most significant among them is the country's income level, or in other words, its gross domestic product (GDP). It is widely documented that economically developed countries with higher income levels allocate more resources to healthcare services.

In addition to human capital, another crucial factor influencing economic growth is the natural resources possessed by a country (Sabir, 2010). In this context, the example of Norway is noteworthy: with a per capita income of 75,420 USD according to the Atlas method (WB – WDI, 2019), Norway ranks among the wealthiest countries globally. Its wealth is largely attributed to its effective and efficient utilization of oil and natural gas resources through a skilled labor force and technological advancements. Furthermore, Norway has successfully directed export revenues derived from these resources predominantly toward savings and infrastructure investments, thereby enhancing its economic prosperity.

Table 1

Global Natural Gas and Oil Reserves by Country

No	Country (Natural Gas)	Reserves (Trillion m ³)	Share (%)	Country (Oil)	Reserves (Billion tons)	Share (%)
1	Russian Federation	38.0	19.1%	Venezuela	48.0	17.5%
2	Iran	32.0	16.1%	Saudi Arabia	40.9	17.2%
3	Qatar	24.7	12.4%	Canada	27.3	9.8%
4	Turkmenistan	19.5	9.8%	Iran	21.4	9.0%
5	United States	12.9	6.5%	Iraq	19.6	8.4%
6	China	8.4	4.2%	Russian Federation	14.7	6.2%
7	Venezuela	6.3	3.2%	Kuwait	14.0	5.9%
8	Saudi Arabia	6.0	3.0%	United Arab Emirates	13.0	5.6%
9	United Arab Emirates	5.9	3.0%	United States	8.2	4.0%
10	Nigeria	5.4	2.7%	Libya	6.3	2.8%
11	Algeria	4.3	2.2%	Nigeria	5.0	2.1%
12	Iraq	3.5	1.8%	Kazakhstan	3.9	1.7%
13	Azerbaijan	2.8	1.4%	China	3.6	1.5%
14	Kazakhstan	2.7	1.3%	Qatar	2.6	1.5%
15	Australia	2.4	1.2%	Brazil	1.8	0.7%
16	Egypt	2.1	1.1%	Algeria	1.5	0.7%
17	Canada	2.0	1.0%	Angola	1.1	0.5%
18	Kuwait	1.7	0.9%	Norway	1.1	0.5%
19	Norway	1.5	0.8%	Azerbaijan	1.0	0.4%
20	Libya	1.4	0.7%	—	—	—
	Total	183.6	92.4%		235.0	95.9%

(BP, 2020)

The Relationship Between Natural Resources and Economic Development

Natural resources, particularly non-renewable energy sources, play a strategic role in a country's economic development process. However, 95.9% of the world's oil reserves and 92.4% of its natural gas reserves are controlled by only twenty-two countries (BP, 2020). As shown in Table 1, not every country possesses such resources, and among those that do, not all are socioeconomically comparable to countries like Norway. In fact, some resource-rich nations struggle to meet even the basic food needs of their populations.

This paradox—resource abundance coexisting with underdevelopment—has been a central debate in the economic literature for decades. Referred to as the “resource curse,” this phenomenon was first conceptualized by British economist Richard Auty. In his research on oil-exporting countries during the period 1970–1985, Auty found that revenues from natural resources tended to lower living standards and increase economic vulnerability (Auty, 2001).

Similarly, the theory of “Dutch Disease”, developed by Max Corden, suggests that while resource-based economies may experience short-term growth surges, they often face declining growth rates—even negative growth—in the long term (Corden, 1984). According to this theory, reliance on resource exports crowds out other key sectors such as agriculture and manufacturing, hindering economic diversification. As

a result, when these resources are depleted or subject to severe price shocks, such economies become highly vulnerable and may face severe financial crises (Aras & Süleymanov, 2010).

Empirical studies on the link between natural resources and economic growth indicate that if the share of natural resource exports exceeds 19% of a country's GDP, the country is considered resource-dependent. This dependence has been found to exert a direct and negative impact on both economic growth rates and per capita income. Sachs and Warner (1997) argue that persistent reliance on natural resources undermines the sustainability of initial growth, with resource-rich countries eventually exhibiting poorer long-term economic performance than resource-poor ones.

In line with this, Sachs and Warner (1995), in their study covering the years 1970–1990, identified a negative correlation between energy export revenues and economic development in some countries. They emphasized that this “resource curse” poses a serious obstacle to building a resilient and sustainable economic structure.

Therefore, when compared to the example of Norway, it becomes evident that natural resource abundance alone does not guarantee development. For instance, Angola—Africa's second-largest oil producer and a country rich in natural gas and diamond reserves—had a per capita income of only \$2,791 in 2019 (WB – WDI, 2019). This underscores that it is not the

mere possession of resources, but how effectively they are managed, that determines a nation's development trajectory.

Azerbaijan's Economy and Healthcare Sector

Natural resources, particularly oil and natural gas, can be considered a "divine blessing" for some countries, while for others they represent a "resource curse." However, these resources positively contribute to development and growth only when they are managed correctly and efficiently. The concentration of irreplaceable energy resources like oil and natural gas in limited geographical areas grants strategic importance to these resource-rich countries, regardless of their development levels. Azerbaijan, a post-Soviet state, is one such country.

After declaring independence in 1991 following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Azerbaijan became historically significant in the oil sector by pioneering numerous "firsts." The country is recognized for the first industrial-scale oil production, the application of drilling methods, the construction of oil pipelines, the establishment of refineries, and offshore oil extraction. In 1942, with a production volume of 24.5 million tons, Azerbaijan accounted for 50% of the world's oil output, playing a decisive role in the Soviet Union's victory over Nazi Germany. Despite the challenges of the early independence years marked by the First Karabakh War, internal political struggles, and economic crises, the situation stabilized following Heydar Aliyev's rise to power. In 1994, Azerbaijan signed a 25-year production sharing agreement, later known as the "Contract of the Century," with major international oil companies including BP, ExxonMobil, and Shell.

Following nearly five years of investments, oil production commenced, and on December 29, 1999, the State Oil Fund of Azerbaijan (SOFAZ) was established by presidential decree. Since 2000, all revenues from oil and gas sales and transit have been collected under SOFAZ. Drawing on experiences from other resource-rich countries, the fund's primary objectives have been the efficient management of accumulating revenues, investment in the country's real economy to ensure the welfare of its citizens and future generations, financing sustainable socio-economic development projects, and supporting the state budget (Long-Term Strategy for the Management of Oil and Gas Revenues, 2005–2025).

Ranked fourth globally among 60 sovereign wealth funds for transparency (Peterson Institute for International Economics, 2016; IFSWF), SOFAZ has managed revenues totaling 165.4 billion USD over two decades. This funding has been utilized to finance critical infrastructure projects, such as the construction of the Oghuz-Gabala-Baku water pipeline, irrigation systems in the Samur-Abşeron region, the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan oil pipeline, the development of the Azeri-Chirag-Guneshli oil fields and Shah Deniz gas field, the "Star" refinery in Turkey, the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway, the South Caucasus pipeline, and the TANAP and TAP gas pipelines. Additionally, SOFAZ has addressed the housing needs of nearly one million displaced persons due to the Karabakh conflict, provided overseas educational scholarships to develop human capital,

made various domestic and international financial investments, and transferred approximately 120 billion USD to the state budget (SOFAZ, 2019). The fund currently manages assets worth approximately 42 billion USD.

As a result of these initiatives, Azerbaijan's economy has undergone a significant transformation since 2000, driven by the expanding oil and gas sector. With increased production and rising oil prices, GDP grew from 5.3 billion USD in 2000 to 75.3 billion USD in 2014. Government budget expenditures increased from 0.8 billion to 19.1 billion AZN, while per capita income rose from 663 to 7,690 USD. Inflation dropped from 12.5% to 1%, and unemployment decreased from 12% to 5%. Maintaining an average annual growth rate of approximately 10%, Azerbaijan recorded one of the world's fastest growth rates at 25.5% in 2007 (WB – WDI, 2019).

Reflections of Economic Progress on the Healthcare Sector

Positive developments in Azerbaijan's economy have also impacted the healthcare sector. Public healthcare services, financed by the central budget and free of charge for citizens, have begun to improve due to ongoing health reforms. New hospitals were established particularly to enhance regional access to healthcare, steps were taken to develop the domestic pharmaceutical, machinery, and equipment industry, the general health insurance system was initiated, and the quality of healthcare services was significantly increased within the financial capacities of the state (State Program on Social and Economic Development of Regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2004–2008).

Examination of health indicators reveals notable improvements. Compared to 2000, the life expectancy at birth increased from 66.8 to 72 years by 2014; infant mortality per 1,000 live births declined from 61.1 to 25; maternal mortality per 10,000 live births decreased from 5.7 to 2.5; tuberculosis incidence per 1,000 people dropped from 6.8 to 0.85; and the human development index rose from 0.635 to 0.756 (WB – WDI, 2019).

However, fluctuations in oil prices directly affect the revenues of oil-producing countries. While price increases benefit producer countries, declines adversely impact their economies and development policies. Despite efforts towards sustainable economic development, Azerbaijan has not reduced the share of the oil sector in GDP below 40% (56.1% in 2007; 48.1% in 2010; 40.9% in 2013). Moreover, in 2014, crude oil and natural gas exports accounted for 66.5% of total exports. The sharp decline in oil prices starting in 2014 severely affected the country's macroeconomic stability. By 2016, GDP had fallen to 37.9 billion USD, per capita income declined to 4,480 USD, and the economy contracted by 3.1%. Inflation rose to 14.6%, external debt increased from 10.6 billion to 16.2 billion USD, and the national currency, the manat, depreciated twice in 2015, losing 117.9% of its value (State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan, 2019).

Over the past decade, a decrease in oil and gas revenues, which constitute at least 50% of central budget revenues, has also affected the budget-financed healthcare sector. The share of government expenditure

allocated to health reached its lowest point of 3.1% in 2018 and peaked at 5.4% in 2005, averaging around 4.1% over the last 20 years. Despite budgetary imbalances, the government has not abandoned health investments; with rising oil prices and relative economic stabilization, the health budget share increased to 4.3% in 2019. Although nominal spending reached a historic high (1.04 billion AZN or 1.3% of GDP), in dollar terms, it remained below the 2014 level of 853 million USD, amounting to 613 million USD.

The healthcare sector's dependence on imported pharmaceuticals, consumables, and machinery has negatively affected its development. Despite population growth (from 9.477 million in 2014 to 9.982 million in 2019), critical health indicators such as total healthcare personnel (declining from 89,300 to 86,500), healthcare personnel per 10,000 people (from 95.6 to 87.7), and hospital beds per 10,000 people (from 47.2 to 44.7) have deteriorated. This underscores once again the crucial role of resource revenues in all sectors of the economy, including healthcare.

Literature Review

Numerous studies have been conducted on oil revenues, prices, and their economic impacts. Darby (1982) examined the relationship between oil prices and macroeconomic variables and argued that this relationship was not significant. In contrast, Hamilton (1983), analyzing U.S. oil prices during the period 1949–1973, found strong evidence of a relationship between oil prices and economic variables. El-Anshasy et al. (2005) focused on Venezuela, one of the world's largest oil producers, and demonstrated that oil price shocks between 1950 and 2001 directly affected the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Farzanegan (2011) analyzed the dynamic effects of oil shocks on public expenditures in Iran from 1959 to 2007, showing that public spending responds significantly to shocks in oil revenues or prices. Similarly, Dizaji (2014) examined the dynamic relationship between public revenues and expenditures in Iran's oil-export-dependent economy and identified a positive linear correlation.

Hamdi and Sbia (2013) empirically investigated the dynamic relationships among oil revenues, government expenditures, and economic growth in Bahrain from 1960 to 2010, emphasizing that oil revenues constitute the main source of economic growth and government spending. Adedokun (2012) analyzed the impact of oil revenues on Nigeria's economic growth between 1975 and 2009 and found that oil export revenues positively influenced growth in both the short and long term. Likewise, Akinlo (2012) assessed the role of oil in Nigeria's economy from 1960 to 2009, providing empirical evidence that oil revenues may foster growth in non-oil sectors excluding industry.

Quixina and Almeida (2014) tested the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Angola, a resource-dependent economy, for the period 1995–2012. Their Granger causality analysis, considering oil and non-oil sectors separately, concluded that Angola's economic growth is driven by revenues from the oil sector. In a study on Kazakhstan, Azhgaliyeva (2014) reported that oil production in-

creases real government expenditures but noted the adverse effects of oil revenues on non-oil industries, attributed to the appreciation of the national currency. Arezki and Ismail (2013) included Azerbaijan in a panel data analysis of 32 oil-exporting countries and found that public expenditures tend to increase when oil prices rise but do not decrease when prices fall. Focusing specifically on Azerbaijan, Hasanov (2010) argued that the oil boom between 2000 and 2007 led to the appreciation of the manat and a decline in non-oil production.

Regarding health expenditures, the literature suggests that economically developed countries tend to allocate more resources to health compared to less developed ones. Therefore, the relationship between income levels and health outcomes has been extensively studied, with health expenditures and income considered important topics in the literature. Preston (1975) illustrated the correlation between income (GDP per capita) and health (life expectancy) during the 1930s and 1960s through a meaningful graph, now known as the "Preston Curve," which demonstrates the correlation coefficients between income and average life expectancy.

Acemoglu et al. (2013) investigated the relationship between income and health expenditures following oil price shocks in the United States and concluded that rising incomes due to increased oil prices did not necessarily lead to higher health expenditures. Govindaraj et al. (1997), studying health expenditures in Latin America and the Caribbean, emphasized that economic development contributes to an increase in health spending in the long run. Hall and Jones (2007) examined the income-health expenditure relationship and found a positive correlation, indicating that health spending rises as income increases.

Ssozi and Amlani (2015) analyzed health sector data from 43 Sub-Saharan African countries between 1995 and 2011 to assess the efficiency of health expenditures. Their findings suggest that improvements in public health services are likely to increase public health expenditures. Jaba et al. (2014) employed panel data analysis for 175 countries from 1995 to 2010, investigating the relationship between health system inputs and outputs, and reported a statistically significant positive association between average life expectancy and public health expenditures. Mou (2013), analyzing 13 OECD countries between 1981 and 2007, identified key factors influencing health expenditures, highlighting that income inequality and aging populations are less strongly related to public health spending compared to other factors.

Literature Review and Research Significance

Although the impact of oil and natural gas revenues—which constitute an average of 40% of GDP—on various sectors of Azerbaijan's economy has been studied, no research has been found examining the relationship between the resource revenues transferred to the central budget by SOFAZ, which constitute an average of 50% of the budget over the years, and budget health expenditures. In this context, the need for empirical studies analyzing the relationship between oil and natural gas revenues and budget health expenditures

and health sector data in Azerbaijan further strengthens the importance of this study.

The main aim of the study is to investigate whether there is a causal relationship, and if so, the direction of this relationship, between resource revenues obtained in the last twenty years and budget health expenditures, total health personnel in the country, the number of physicians per 10,000 people, and the total number of hospital beds. Based on this, the following hypotheses have been developed:

- Hypothesis 1 (H1): As a result of the increase in oil and natural gas revenues, there has been an increase in budget health expenditures between 2000 and 2019.
- Hypothesis 2 (H2): As a result of the increase in oil and natural gas revenues, there has been an increase in the total number of health personnel in the country between 2000 and 2019.
- Hypothesis 3 (H3): As a result of the increase in oil and natural gas revenues, there has been an increase in the number of physicians per 10,000 people between 2000 and 2019.
- Hypothesis 4 (H4): As a result of the increase in oil and natural gas revenues, there has been an increase in the total number of hospital beds in the country between 2000 and 2019.

Research Methodology

To achieve the research objectives, data sets from the 2019 World Energy Reserves Report by British Petroleum, the 2019 health sector data from the State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan, and annual reports prepared by SOFAZ covering the years 2000 – 2019 were used. The effects of the independent variable—oil

and natural gas revenues (PDG) - on the dependent variable - central budget health expenditures (BSH), total hospital beds (THY), total health personnel (TSP), and the number of physicians per 10,000 people (OKH) - were investigated. Additionally, whether a causal relationship exists between oil and natural gas revenues and the other variables was examined, along with the direction of any such relationship.

In line with the study’s objectives, the data related to the above-mentioned variables were analyzed using SPSS 25.0. Since the number of data points was less than 30 (n=20), Spearman correlation analysis was applied. Subsequently, an ANOVA model was used as an initial test to determine the factors affecting the data set, and linear regression models explaining the relationship between statistically significant independent and dependent variables were estimated.

Findings

To determine the direction of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables, the graphical relationships of the variables were first examined. There was a positive linear relationship between PDG and BSH; however, due to the small sample size and the lack of normal distribution in the data set, this relationship was not strictly around a straight line (Graph 1). No relationship was found between PDG and TSP, and the irregular distribution of values confirmed this result. Negative relationships between PDG and THY and between PDG and OKH were observed from the graphs, and the distributions of the data relative to each other indicated that these relationships were weak. To obtain a clearer measurement of the relationship between dependent and independent variables, Spearman correlation analysis was conducted (Table 2).

Graph 1

Descriptive statistics for the variables included in the study show that:

The average value of PDG is 8.27 billion AZN,
 The average value of BSH is 0.42 billion AZN,
 The average TSP is 89.98 thousand people,
 The average OKH is 35.43 per 10,000 people,
 And the average THY is 57.80 thousand units.

Table 2

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
PDG (billion AZN)	8.2705	7.03471	20
BSH (billion AZN)	0.418	0.30903	20
TSP (thousand)	89.975	2.92375	20
OKH (per 10,000)	35.433	1.42681	20
THY (thousand)	57.795	12.418	20

Correlation (Spearman's rho) results between independent variable PDG and dependent variables:

Variable	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-Value (Sig., 1-tailed)	N
BSH	0.831**	0.000	20
TSP	-0.011	0.481	20
OKH	-0.398*	0.041	20
THY	-0.893**	0.000	20

Hypothesis Results:

- **H1:** An increase in oil and gas revenues led to an increase in budget health expenditures between 2000 and 2019. Correlation analysis showed a significant positive relationship between the increase in oil and gas revenues and budget health expenditures during this period ($r = 0.831$, $p < 0.05$). In other words, as oil and gas revenues increase, budget health expenditures also increase.

- **H2:** An increase in oil and gas revenues led to an increase in total health personnel between 2000 and 2019. The analysis showed no significant relationship between oil and gas revenues and total health personnel during this period ($p > 0.05$).

- **H3:** An increase in oil and gas revenues led to an increase in the number of physicians per 10,000 people between 2000 and 2019. Correlation analysis showed a significant but negative relationship between increased oil revenues and the number of physicians per 10,000 people ($r = -0.398$, $p < 0.05$). That is, as oil revenues increased, this ratio decreased.

- **H4:** An increase in oil and gas revenues led to an increase in total hospital beds between 2000 and 2019. Correlation analysis showed a significant but negative relationship between the increase in natural resource revenues and total hospital beds ($r = -0.893$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, as oil revenues increased, the total number of hospital beds decreased.

Linear regression analysis was applied and models were established to reveal the effects of the independent variable on the dependent variables. In the regression analysis examining the effect of PDG on BSH, the ANOVA table results showed a significance value of $p < 0.05$, indicating that the established model is statistically significant. The model summary table shows an R^2 of 0.752, meaning that 75% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable. According to the coefficients table, since the significance value is $p < 0.05$, the increase in oil and gas revenues positively affects budget health expenditures, increasing them by approximately 4%.

Table 3

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1.364	1	1.364	54.504	.000b
Residual	.450	18	.025		
Total	1.815	19			

a. Dependent Variable: BSH (billion AZN)

b. Predictors: (Constant), PDG (billion AZN)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.867a	.752	.738	.15820

- a. Predictors: (Constant), PDG (billion AZN)
- b. Dependent Variable: BSH (billion AZN)

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	(Constant) 0.103	0.055		1.858
	PDG 0.038	0.005	0.867	7.383

Model Prediction (MP): $BSH = 0.103 + 0.038 \times PDG$

Since there was no relationship between the increase in PDG and TSP, no effect was observed in the regression analysis. The ANOVA table's significance value (0.743) is $p > 0.05$, indicating insignificance, so the regression analysis was not continued.

Table 4

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.991	1	0.991	0.111
	Residual	161.426	18	8.968	
	Total	162.417	19		

- a. Dependent Variable: TSP (thousand people)
- b. Predictors: (Constant), PDG (mln AZN)

According to the results of the regression analysis conducted to examine the effect of PDG on TSP, the ANOVA table shows a significance value of $p = 0.743$, which is greater than 0.05. Thus, the established model is found to be not statistically significant.

Table 5

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10.048	1	10.048	6.317
	Residual	28.632	18	1.591	
	Total	38.680	19		

- a. Dependent Variable: PHPR
- b. Predictors: (Constant), PDG (mln AZN)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.510a	0.260	0.219	1.26122

- a. Predictors: (Constant), PDG (mln AZN)
- b. Dependent Variable: PHPR

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig.
(Constant)	36.288	0.442		82.123	0.000
PDG	-0.103	0.041	-0.510	-2.513	0.022

Regression Equation: $PHPR = 36.288 - 0.103 \times PDG$

The regression analysis conducted to determine the effect of PDG on PHPR reveals a significance value of $p = 0.022$, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the model is **statistically significant**. The coefficient of determination is $R^2 = 0.26$, indicating that 26% of the var-

iance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable. However, since this value is below 0.70, the model is considered **insufficiently explanatory**. The coefficients table shows that an increase in PDG has a **negative effect** on PHPR, and that rising petroleum revenues are associated with a **10% decrease in the number of physicians per 10,000 population**.

Table 6

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1875.465	1	1875.465	32.015
	Residual	1054.464	18	58.581	
	Total	2929.930	19		

a. Dependent Variable: THB (thousand)

b. Predictors: (Constant), PDG (mln AZN)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.800a	0.640	0.620	7.65385

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig.
(Constant)	69.476	2.682		25.909	0.000
PDG	-1.412	0.250	-0.800	-5.658	0.000

Regression Equation: $THB = 69.476 - 1.412 \times PDG$

According to the results of the regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of PDG on THB, the significance value of $p = 0.000$ indicates that the model is statistically significant. The coefficient of determination is $R^2 = 0.64$, meaning that 64% of the variation in THB is explained by PDG. However, since this is below the 70% threshold, the model is considered moderately explanatory. The coefficients indicate a negative relationship, where increases in oil and gas revenues lead to a 1.4-unit decrease in the total number of hospital beds.

Conclusion

The results of this study have shown that natural resource revenues have a significant impact on the health sector as well as many other areas of the Azerbaijani economy. The analysis revealed a strong linear and positive relationship between oil and natural gas revenues and budget-funded health expenditures. Countries dependent on natural resources aiming for economic growth must increase the share of sectors such as industry, services, agriculture, and tourism in the gross national product and exports. On the other hand, development is a multidimensional concept that should be evaluated not only quantitatively but also socially and politically, with the ultimate goal of improving the quality of life in society. It is evident from the experiences of many resource-rich countries that natural resource wealth alone is not sufficient to achieve development.

Although alternative energy sources are gaining importance today, projections on energy consumption by the International Energy Agency (IEA) and BP Energy (Current Scenario) indicate that oil and coal will maintain their effectiveness in the future, while the share of natural gas is expected to increase. Another important point in these projections is that oil reserves have an average lifespan of 30 years, and natural gas reserves approximately 50 years. These assessments are based on current conditions, but it is certain that oil and natural gas resources are not infinite. Countries like

Azerbaijan, which are heavily dependent on natural resource revenues for their economic development, must anticipate the consequences of this reality and take measures to mitigate its effects.

This situation offers a second chance for Azerbaijan, which ranks 13th in the world based on the size of newly discovered and confirmed natural gas reserves. Efficient and effective use of Azerbaijan's natural resource revenues, accelerating sectoral development beyond oil and gas to reduce resource dependency, and increasing employment in these fields require educated and healthy individuals who can manage resources. In other words, natural resources can only be transformed into added value through the presence of educated and healthy individuals, and institutions with strong management skills and institutional quality.

Therefore, long-term and applicable development policies, especially in the health sector, should be designed to improve the quality of life and allocate more financial resources to health. Only then can natural resources become a long-term blessing, as seen in countries like Norway or Canada. To achieve this, Azerbaijan has prepared and implemented the "Strategic Roadmap for the National Economy and Perspectives of the Republic of Azerbaijan" and the "State Program for Socio-Economic Development of the Regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2019-2023," which foresee post-crisis socio-economic development.

It is also noteworthy that health expenditures of 828.8 million USD (1.409 million AZN) planned in the 2021 central public budget reached their highest level since 2014 (853.0 million USD).

References

1. Acemoglu, D., Finkelstein, A., & Notowidigdo, M. J. (2013). Income and health spending: Evidence from oil price shocks. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 95(4), 1079–1095.
2. Adedokun, A. (2012). Oil export and economic growth: Descriptive analysis and empirical evidence from Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(1), 46–58.

3. Akinlo, A. (2012). How important is oil in Nigeria's economic growth? *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 5, 165–179.
4. Aras, N., Süleymanov, E., & Zeynalov, A. (2012). Azərbaycan enerji kaynakları gelirlerinin ülke ekonomisine etkisi. *Çankırı Karatekin Üniversitesi Uluslararası Avrasya Strateji Dergisi*, 2(2), 001–028.
5. Aliyev R.M., Hasanzade R.Sh., The role of fiscal policy in economic regulation. *Journal Sciences of Europe (Praha, Czech Republic) No 159 (2025)*, p 3-9
6. Arezki, R., & İsmail, K. (2013). Boom-bust cycle, asymmetrical fiscal response and Dutch disease. *Journal of Development Economics*, 101, 256–267.
7. Auty, R. (1998). Resource abundance and economic development: Improving the performance of resource-rich countries (73 p.). UNU-Wider.
8. Azərbaycan Dövlət Statistika Komitəsi. (n.d.). System of national accounts. https://www.stat.gov.az/source/system_nat_accounts/
9. Azərbaycan Cumhuriyeti. (2016). Milli ekonomisi və perspektifləri üzrə strateji yol haritası.
10. Azərbaycan Cumhuriyeti. (2019). Regionlarının 2019–2023 yıllarda sosyal – iktisadi inkişafı devlet programı.
11. Azərbaycan Cumhuriyeti. (2004). Regionlarının sosyal – iktisadi inkişafı devlet programı (2004–2008 yıllar).
12. Azhgaliyeva, D. (2014). The effect of fiscal policy on the oil revenue fund: The case of Kazakhstan. *Journal of Eurasian Studies*, 5, 157–183.
13. BP. (2020). Statistical review of world energy 2020 (69th ed.). <https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/energy-economics/statistical-review/bp-stats-review-2019-full-report.pdf>
14. Corden, M. (1984). Booming sector and Dutch disease economics: Survey and consolidation. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 36, 359–380.
15. Darby, M. R. (1982). The price of oil and world inflation and recession. *The American Economic Review*, 72(4), 738–751.
16. Dizaji, S. F. H. (2014). The effects of oil shocks on government expenditures and government revenue nexus (with an application to Iran's sanctions). *Economic Modelling*, 40, 299–313.
17. El-Anshasy, A., Bradley, M. D., & Joutz, F. (2005). Evidence on the role of oil prices in Venezuela's economic performance: 1950–2001. Working Paper, University of Washington.
18. Farzanegan, M. R. (2011). Oil revenue shocks and government spending behavior in Iran. *Energy Economics*, 33, 1055–1069.
19. Govindaraj, R., Chellaraj, G., & Murray, C. J. L. (1997). Health expenditures in Latin America and the Caribbean. *Social Science & Medicine*, 44(2), 157–169.
20. Hall, R. E., & Jones, C. I. (2007). The value of life and the rise in health spending. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 122(1), 39–72.
21. Hamdi, H., & Sbia, R. (2013). Dynamic relationships between oil revenues, government spending and economic growth in an oil-dependent economy. *Economic Modelling*, 35, 118–125.
22. Hamilton, J. D. (1983). Oil and the macroeconomy since World War II. *Journal of Political Economy*, 91(2), 228–248.
23. Hasanov, F. (2010). The impact of real oil price on real effective exchange rate: The case of Azerbaijan (Discussion Paper). German Institute for Economic Research (DIW Berlin).
24. International Forum of Sovereign Wealth Funds. (n.d.). Members: Azerbaijan. <https://www.ifswf.org/members/azerbaijan>
25. Jaba, E., Balan, C. B., & Robu, I. B. (2014). The relationship between life expectancy at birth and health expenditures estimated by a cross-country and time-series analysis. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 15, 108–114.
26. Mou, H. (2013). The political economy of the public–private mix in health expenditure: An empirical review of thirteen OECD countries. *Health Policy*, 113(3), 270–283.
27. Petrol və Doğalgaz Gelirlerinin Yönetilmesi Üzrə Uzun Müddetli Stratejiya (2005–2025 yıllar). (n.d.).
28. Preston, S. (1975). The changing relation between mortality and level of economic development. *Population Studies*, 29(2), 231–248.
29. Sabır, H. (2010). Azgelişmiş ülkelerde rekabet ve kalkınma. Derin Yayınları.
30. Sachs, J., & Warner, A. (1995). Natural resource abundance and economic growth (NBER Working Paper No. W5398).
31. Sachs, J., & Warner, A. (1997). Natural resource abundance and economic growth. Center for International Development and Harvard Institute for International Development, Harvard University.
32. SOFAZ. (2000–2019). Reports and statistics. <https://oilfund.az/report-and-statistics>
33. Ssozi, J., & Amlani, S. (2015). The effectiveness of health expenditure on the proximate and ultimate goals of healthcare in Sub-Saharan Africa. *World Development*, 165–179.
34. Quixina, Y., & Almeida, A. (2014). Financial development and economic growth in a natural resource based economy: Evidence from Angola (FEP Working Paper No. 542).
35. World Bank. (2019a). Azerbaijan data. <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?source=2&country=AZE>
36. World Bank. (2019b). GDP per capita, Norway. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD?locations=NO>
37. World Bank. (2019c). GDP per capita, Angola. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD?locations=AO>
38. World Bank. (2019d). Health data: Azerbaijan. <https://data.worldbank.org/topic/health?end=2018&locations=AZ&start=2000>